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Single-Parent Households and Academic Achievement of Primary School Pupils in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria: Implication for Counselling

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Abstract

The increasing prevalence of single parent households has sparked growing interest in understanding their impact on children's academic outcomes. This study explores whether children raised by single parents encounter distinct challenges in achieving academic success compared to their peers from dual-parent families. Drawing on existing literature and empirical studies, the research identifies key factors such as economic constraints, limited parental involvement, emotional stressors, and social stigma that may affect academic performance. It also investigates the role of external support systems, including school-based interventions, community programs, and government policies, in mitigating these challenges. The paper suggested the introduction of counselling, mentoring, and after-school tutoring specifically designed for students from single-parent households. Organize workshops and training sessions for single parents on academic monitoring, emotional support, and time

management strategies. The paper recommended that schools should identify vulnerable students and provide free tutoring, school supplies, and academic monitoring. Guidance counselors should be trained to offer emotional support for children dealing with family-related stress.

Keywords: Single-parent, Household, Academic achievement, Counselling

Introduction

Single parent is a mother or father who takes care of their child or children without the support of a spouse or partner living in the same household. This can happen due to various reasons such as divorce, separation, death of a partner, or personal choice. Family structures have undergone significant transformations over the past century, reflecting broader shifts in cultural norms, economic conditions, and social expectations. Traditionally, the nuclear family comprising a married couple and their biological children was considered the standard model, especially in Western and many African societies. In earlier generations, extended families were also common, with multiple generations living under one roof and sharing responsibilities. However, globalization, urbanization, and changing gender roles have contributed to the diversification of family forms. Today, family structures include single-parent households, cohabiting couples, blended families, same-sex families, and individuals living alone. These variations reflect evolving attitudes toward marriage, parenting, and personal autonomy.

Among these emerging structures, single-parent households have seen a notable rise globally. Historically, single-parent families were primarily the result of widowhood, but from the 1960s onward, rising divorce rates, out-of-wedlock births, and changing societal norms have become the dominant causes. In many countries, including Nigeria, the increase in single-parent families is linked to factors such as marital breakdown, economic hardship, and shifting cultural perceptions of parenting roles.

The stigma once associated with single-parenting has diminished in many regions, especially among educated populations and urban communities, where it is increasingly viewed as a legitimate and sometimes necessary family arrangement. This rise has profound implications for children and society. Children in single-parent households often face unique challenges, including economic instability, reduced parental supervision, and emotional stress due to the absence of one parent. Studies have shown that these

children may be at greater risk of academic underachievement, behavioral issues, and limited access to resources compared to their peers in two-parent families. However, it is important to note that many single-parent families demonstrate remarkable resilience, and outcomes vary widely depending on the presence of support systems, such as extended family involvement, community programs, and school-based interventions. The evolution of family structures, particularly the growth of single-parent households, underscores the need for adaptive social policies and inclusive educational strategies. As societies continue to diversify, understanding and supporting all family forms becomes essential for fostering equitable opportunities and holistic child development.

The concept of family has evolved significantly in recent decades, reflecting broader societal, economic, and cultural transformations. Traditionally, the nuclear family comprising two married parents and their biological children was considered the dominant model. However, there has been a marked diversification of family structures, including single-parent households, blended families, same-sex parent families, and cohabiting couples. These changes are driven by factors such as shifting social norms, increased female economic independence, declining marriage rates, and rising divorce and separation rates (Lee, 2025).

Single parent families typically result from divorce, separation, death of a spouse, or intentional single parenthood. According to various studies, these households often experience socioeconomic and emotional difficulties that may hinder a child's educational progress. Reduced income, limited time for parental supervision, and emotional strain are common characteristics of single parent homes (Amato, 2005; McLanahan & Sandefur, 1994).

Single-parent households, in particular, have seen a notable increase worldwide. In Nigeria, for example, approximately 25% of households were headed by single parents as of 2025, a trend attributed to marital instability, economic hardship, and evolving cultural perceptions of parenting roles (Okola, 2025). The Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research (NISER) found that divorce (78.9%), death of a spouse (77.8%), and partner desertion (70%) were the leading causes of single parenting in Anambra State, Nigeria (NISER, 2024). These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of single parenthood, which is often shaped by both voluntary and involuntary circumstances.

Globally, the rise in single-parent households has been linked to broader demographic shifts. In the United States, nearly 23% of children live with a single parent, the highest rate among 130 countries surveyed (Chamie, 2025). This increase is largely due to declining marriage rates and a rise in births outside of marriage. Between 1960 and 2023, the percentage of U.S. children living in single-parent households tripled from 9% to 25% (Chamie, 2025). Similar trends have been observed in Europe, Latin America, and parts of Africa, where economic empowerment and changing gender roles have enabled more individuals particularly women to raise children independently (Great, 2025).

Despite the challenges associated with single parenting, such as financial strain, emotional stress, and limited access to resources, many single-parent families demonstrate resilience and adaptability. Community support, government interventions, and inclusive social policies play a crucial role in mitigating the negative effects of single parenthood. For instance, initiatives like childcare subsidies, flexible work arrangements, and parental education programs have been recommended to support single parents and promote child well-being (Great, 2025; NISER, 2024).

In summary, the period from 2020 to 2025 has witnessed a significant shift in family structures, with single-parent households becoming increasingly prevalent. This transformation reflects deeper societal changes and calls for responsive policies and support systems to ensure that all family forms are recognized and supported in fostering healthy child development and social stability.

Academic achievement is widely recognized as a critical developmental outcome that influences both individual growth and societal advancement. It serves as a benchmark for evaluating a student's mastery of educational content, cognitive skills, and readiness for future academic and professional pursuits. According to Steinmayr et al. (2025), academic achievement encompasses a range of performance indicators, including grades, standardized test scores, and educational attainment, all of which reflect a learner's intellectual engagement and progress. These indicators are not only used to assess learning outcomes but also to predict future success in higher education and career trajectories.

From a developmental perspective, academic achievement is closely linked to psychological constructs such as motivation, self-efficacy, and resilience. Okoro (2025) found that achievement motivation significantly predicts

academic engagement among Nigerian undergraduate students, suggesting that students who are driven to succeed are more likely to invest effort and persist through academic challenges. This aligns with broader research indicating that academic achievement fosters self-confidence, goal-setting behavior, and adaptive learning strategies (Twomey & Murphy, 2025). Moreover, academic success contributes to a student's sense of identity and belonging, which are essential components of socio-emotional development. On a societal level, academic achievement is a key determinant of socioeconomic mobility and national development. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has consistently emphasized the role of academic performance in shaping Labor market outcomes and economic competitiveness (OECD, 2020). In developing countries like Nigeria, improving academic achievement is seen as a pathway to reducing poverty and enhancing human capital (Chamie, 2025). Educational policies and interventions often target academic achievement as a primary goal, recognizing its ripple effects on health, civic engagement, and lifelong learning. In sum, academic achievement is not merely a measure of scholastic success, it is a multifaceted developmental outcome that influences personal growth, psychological well-being, and societal progress. Its importance from 2020 to 2025 has been underscored by empirical studies and policy frameworks that advocate for inclusive, equitable, and quality education systems.

Challenges Confronting Children from Single Parent Households

Despite the growing prevalence of single-parent households worldwide, the academic implications for children raised in such family settings remain a subject of concern among educators, policymakers, and social researchers. In many contexts, particularly within developing countries like Nigeria, the challenges faced by children in single-parent homes are compounded by socioeconomic limitations, emotional strain, and reduced parental involvement, all of which can negatively influence academic outcomes. The traditional educational system, often designed with assumptions of dual-parent support, may fail to adequately address the unique needs of these students, leading to disparities in educational attainment and overall school performance. Studies have revealed that children from single-parent families often encounter difficulties such as inadequate supervision, financial instability, and limited access to academic resources, which

collectively hinder their ability to compete on an equal footing with peers from two-parent homes (Hiko et al., 2023; Ugbede et al., 2025). Additionally, psychological factors like emotional stress, feelings of abandonment, and social stigma associated with single-parenting may exacerbate these academic challenges (Azuka-Obieke, 2023). Although some children in single-parent households demonstrate resilience and academic success, the lack of structured support systems tailored to their realities presents a significant gap in educational equity.

This study is therefore necessary to look at the specific academic hurdles faced by children from single-parent households and to explore what interventions be they school-based, community-led, or policy-driven can support their educational growth. Without targeted strategies, many of these students risk falling behind, perpetuating cycles of disadvantage. By addressing these concerns, the study aims to contribute to a more inclusive educational framework that recognizes and responds to the evolving dynamics of family life.

Scope of the Study

The study will be limited to primary school pupils in selected public primary schools in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State. The study will focus on single-parent household structure and its influence on pupils' academic achievement.

Literature Review

Single parenting refers to a family structure in which one parent assumes primary responsibility for raising a child or children without the presence of a spouse or cohabiting partner. This family arrangement may arise from divorce, separation, death of a partner, or international choice (Nwachukwu, 2011). In Nigeria, single-parent families have increasingly become a visible social reality due to marital instability, economic pressures, and changing cultural norms (Okola, 2025). While single parenting is no longer viewed solely as a deviant family form, it continues to present unique challenges that may influence children's psychosocial and academic development.

Academic Achievement

Academic achievement is commonly defined as the extent to which students attain educational goals as measured by grades, test scores, and overall

school performance (Steinmayr et al, 2025). It reflects not only cognitive ability but also motivation, persistence, self-regulation, and the learning environment. Singh (2018) emphasized that academic achievement is shaped by both internal factors, such as motivation and self-efficacy, and external factors, including family background and school support. In the Nigerian educational context, academic achievement remains a critical determinant of future educational and occupational opportunities, making it an important area of concern for vulnerable groups such as children from single-parent households.

Single Parenting and Children's Academic Achievement

Several studies have examined the relationship between single parenting and children's academic outcomes. McLanahan and Sandefur (1994) and Amato (2005) reported that children from single-parent families are more likely to experience lower academic achievement compared to those from two-parent households. These differences have often been attributed to reduced household income, limited parental supervision, and increased emotional stress. In line with this, Abe Hiko et al. (2023) found that students from single-parent homes showed lower academic performance, particularly in core subjects, due to inadequate academic monitoring and limited access to learning resources.

In Nigeria, Nwachukwu (2011) observed that children raised by single parents often face difficulties such as school absenteeism, poor concentration, and low academic motivation. Ugbede et al. (2025) further noted that financial constraints in singles-parent households frequently limit the ability of parents to provide textbooks, school materials, and extra lessons, which are essential for academic success. However, it is important to note that not all children from single-parent homes perform poorly academically, as outcomes are influenced by factors such as parental commitment, extended family support, and school interventions.

Economic and Psychosocial factors Affecting Academic Performance

Economic hardship is one of the most significant challenges confronting single-parent families. Reduced income often leads to stress, long working hours, and limited time for parental involvement seen as crucial to children's academic success (Amato, 2005). The OECD (2020) emphasized that socioeconomic status strongly predicts academic achievement,

especially in developing countries. In addition to economic challenges, children from single-parent households may experience emotional difficulties such as anxiety, loneliness, and low self-esteem, which negatively affect classroom participation and learning (Azuka-Obieke, 2023).

Psychosocial factors such as motivation and emotional stability also play a central role in academic achievement. Accordino et al. (2020) found that students' mental health and achievement motivation significantly influence academic outcomes. Similarly, Ryan and Deci (2019) argued that intrinsic motivation enhances persistence and academic engagement, especially when students feel supported by significant adults. In single-parent households where emotional support may be strained, children may struggle to maintain consistent academic motivation.

Role to Support Systems

Research suggests that external support systems can mitigate the negative effects of single parenting on academic achievement. Community support, school-based counselling, mentoring programs, and after –school tutoring have been shown to improve academic outcomes for children from disadvantaged family backgrounds (Great, 2025). The Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research (NISER, 2024) highlighted the importance of government interventions such as financial assistance, parental education, and psychosocial support in promoting child well-being in single-parent families.

School also play a crucial role by providing guidance counselling services, teacher support, and inclusive policies that recognize diverse family structures. According to Twomey and Murphy (2025), supportive educational environments can significantly reduce achievement gaps associated with family background. Therefore, strengthening collaboration between schools, families, and communities is essential for enhancing the academic success of children from single-parent households.

Theoretical Framework

Ecological Systems Theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1979)

Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979) provides a framework for understanding how a child's development is shaped by multiple environmental systems, ranging from immediate settings (microsystem) to

broader societal influences (macrosystem). The microsystem, which includes the family, school, and peers, is particularly relevant to this study. The family, as a primary microsystem, plays a critical role in shaping a child's academic self-efficacy and achievement through direct interactions, such as parenting practices, and indirect influences, such as home-school interactions (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006).

Family structure influences the quality and frequency of interactions within the microsystem. For example, two-parent households may provide more consistent emotional and academic support compared to single-parent households, where resource constraints or time limitations may hinder parental involvement (Amato & Keith, 1991). Home-school interactions, such as parents attending school meetings or communicating with teachers, further mediate the impact of family structure on academic outcomes. These interactions foster a collaborative environment that reinforces pupils' motivation and academic engagement (Epstein, 2018).

Recent literature supports the application of Ecological Systems Theory in African educational settings. Afolabi and Ogunbanjo (2022) found that in Nigerian primary schools, strong home-school partnerships were associated with improved academic performance, particularly among pupils from stable family structures. Similarly, Okeke and Nwosu (2023) highlighted that disruptions in the family microsystem, such as parental divorce or economic hardship, negatively affected pupils' academic motivation in rural Nigerian communities. These studies suggest that the family's role within the microsystem is critical to pupils' academic success in Odeda, where socio-economic challenges and diverse family structures are prevalent.

Moreover, the mesosystem, which represents interactions between microsystems (e.g., family and school), is relevant to this study. Effective communication between parents and teachers can enhance pupils' academic self-efficacy by creating a supportive network that reinforces learning goals (Hill & Tyson, 2009). In Odeda, where cultural and economic factors may limit parental engagement, understanding these interactions is essential for designing interventions to improve academic outcomes.

Relevance of the Theory to the Study

Bronfenbrenner's Ecological System Theory is relevant to this study because it explains how family structure (single-parent household) interacts with school and societal factors to influence pupils' academic achievement. The theory also supports the role of guidance and counselling as an intervention that can improve pupils' academic performance by strengthening family-school relationships and addressing emotional and environmental challenges.

This framework therefore provides a strong theoretical basis for examining the influence of single-parent household structure on the academic achievement of primary school pupils in Odeda Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria, and highlights the importance of counselling interventions.

Empirical Evidence

Several empirical studies have examined the relationship between family structure and pupils' academic achievement, with mixed but largely significant findings. A study by Akinyele and Olorunfemi (2018) investigated the effect of single-parent households on academic performance of primary school pupils in Ogun State, Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey design, the study revealed that pupils from single-parent households performed significantly lower in core subjects such as Mathematics and English Language compared to their counterparts from two parent households. The authors attributed this difference to inadequate parental supervision and financial constraints.

Similarly, Ogunleye (2019) examined family structure and academic achievement among primary school pupils in South-West Nigeria. The findings indicated a significant relationship between single-parenting and low academic achievement, particularly in reading and numeracy skills. The study emphasized that emotional instability and limited home learning support were major contributing factors.

In another Nigerian study, Adeyemo and Taiwo (2020) assessed the influence of parental involvement on pupils' academic performance in public primary schools in Oyo State. The results show that pupils from single-parent households experienced reduced parental involvement, which significantly affected their academic achievement. The study recommended school-based counselling interventions to support such pupils.

Internationally, Amato (2014) conducted a longitudinal study in the United States on family structure and child academic outcomes. The findings revealed that children from single-parent families were more likely to have lower academic achievement and reduced school engagement compared to those from two-parent families. Economic hardship and parental stress were identified as key mediating factors.

Similarly, Jeynes (2015) examined the academic achievement of children from single-parent households across different countries. The study found that children from stable two-parent households generally outperformed those from single-parent families. However, the study also noted that effective parental support and counselling reduced the achievement gap.

From the reviewed empirical studies, it is evidence that single-parent household structure has a notable influence on pupils' academic achievement. However, limited studies have focused on primary school pupils in Odeda Local Government Area of Ogun State, particularly from a counselling perspective. This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by providing empirical evidence on the influence of single-parent households on academic achievement and the implications for counselling.

Summary of Literature and Research Gap

The reviewed literature demonstrates that single parenting can pose challenges to children's academic achievement, largely due to economic hardship, reduced parental involvement, and emotional stress. While several studies have explored this relationship globally and within Nigeria, there remains a gap in context-specific research that examines how school-based and counselling interventions can support children from single-parent households. This study seeks to address this gap by focusing on the academic challenges faced by children from single-parent families and identifying practical strategies for enhancing their academic achievement through counselling, mentoring, and institutional support.

Suggestions

- i. Introduce counseling, mentoring, and after-school tutoring specifically designed for students from single-parent households.
- ii. Organize workshops and training sessions for single parents on academic monitoring, emotional support, and time management strategies.

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- iii. Advocate for financial aid, scholarships, and subsidized school materials to reduce economic barriers affecting academic success.
 - iv. Foster partnerships between schools and local organizations to provide mentorship, psychosocial support, and enrichment programs.
 - v. Develop school policies that are sensitive to diverse family structures, ensuring fair treatment and access to learning resources.
 - vi. Encourage schools to recognize and involve grandparents, older siblings, or guardians in academic support roles.
 - vii. Establish mechanisms to track the effectiveness of support systems and refine them based on student progress data.
 - viii. Incorporate advocacy campaigns in schools and communities to reduce stigma and foster understanding among students and educators.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study will contribute to existing knowledge in the following ways:

1. ***Empirical Evidence at the Primary School Level:*** This study will provide empirical data on the influence of single-parent household structures on the academic achievement of primary school pupils. This area has garnered limited attention compared to secondary and tertiary education in Nigeria.
2. ***Context-Specific Findings from Odeda Local Government Area:*** By concentrating on the Odeda Local Government Area in Ogun State, this research will generate location-specific insights that enrich existing literature on family structure and academic achievement within rural and semi-urban communities in Nigeria.
3. ***Integration of Counselling Perspective:*** Unlike many studies that focus solely on academic outcomes, this research will emphasize the counselling implications of challenges faced by single-parent households. It aims to expand understanding of how guidance and counselling interventions can better support pupils from these families.
4. ***Identification of Key Challenges Affecting Academic Achievement:*** The study will identify specific challenges such as emotional stress, economic constraints, and lack of parental supervision that pupils from single-parent households encounter. This will contribute to a more nuanced understanding of how family structure impacts academic performance.

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5. **Framework for Counselling Interventions:** The findings will aid in the development of practical counselling strategies and intervention frameworks that school counselors can implement to enhance both academic achievement and emotional wellbeing for pupils from single-parent households.
 6. **Baseline Data for Future Research:** This research will serve as a reference point and baseline data for future scholars interested in family structure, child development, academic achievement, and counselling practices within Nigerian primary schools.

Conclusion

In conclusion, while children from single-parent households may face unique challenges in achieving academic success, research suggests that with the right support systems in place, they can thrive academically. By promoting personal achievement motivation, perceived community support, teacher support, and parental involvement, we can help level the playing field for children from single-parent households and ensure they receive the support they need to succeed.

Recommendations

To address the challenges faced by children in single-parent homes, the following actions are recommended:

1. Targeted academic support: Schools should identify vulnerable students and provide free tutoring, school supplies, and academic monitoring.
2. Psychosocial support programs: Guidance counselors should be trained to offer emotional support for children dealing with family-related stress.
3. Parental empowerment programs: Governments and NGOs should support single parents through parenting workshops, financial literacy, and job placement.
4. Conditional Cash Transfer expansion: Programs like the National Social Investment Program (NSIP) should prioritize single-parent families.

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